

A boundary value problem of arbitrary orders involving differential inclusion and a nonlocal fractional-order integral condition

HAMEDA MOHAMED ALAMA¹ and MUSTAFA OMRAN ALSHRANI²

¹ Faculty of Science, Alasmarya Islamic University, Libya

² Faculty of Science, Al-Mergib University, Libya

¹a.alaeamu@asmarya.edu.ly

²moalshrani@elmergib.edu.ly

¹Correspondence : HAMEDA MOHAMED ALAMA.

Email:a.alaeamu@asmarya.edu.ly

Abstract

In the class of continuous functions, we consider a boundary value problem of fractional-order differential inclusion with a nonlocal fractional-order integral condition. Several existing results are provided for the nonlocal boundary value problem. It is demonstrated that both maximal and minimal solutions are possible. Furthermore, the sufficient conditions for the uniqueness and continuity of the solution are investigated.

Keywords: differential inclusion; boundary value problem; Schauder fixed-point theorem; maximal and minimal solutions; continuous dependence.

1. Introduction

The possibility of solving nonlocal problems of fractional orders has been discussed by many authors. See, for instance, refs.([4], [5],[6], [7],[8], [9], [19] and [17]). Different researchers have studied the existence and uniqueness results of differential equations and inclusions with nonlocal boundary conditions using different techniques (see [7],[8], [9],[13], [19] and the references therein). Using m-point boundary conditions, Bai [3] studied fractional differential equations. In a resonance case, Kosmatov [15] investigated the fractional order of three BVP points using the same method. The a priori estimate method has been applied to a nonlocal, nonlinear fractional differential equation with a weak and unique solution [1]. Based on the Monch fixed-point theorem and techniques for measuring noncompactness, Subashini et al. [18] demonstrate the nonlocal fractional integro-differential problem of the Hilfer type. In [4], existence results under mixed Lipschitz and Caratheodory conditions have been presented for functional integro-differential equations of fractional orders, and some properties of the solution are demonstrated.

Here, we focus on solving the boundary value problem of nonlinear differential inclusions

of arbitrary (fractional) orders.

$$\frac{dx}{dt} \in F_1(t, D^\alpha x(t), D^\beta f_2(t, I^\gamma x(t))) \quad \alpha, \beta, \gamma \in (0, 1], \quad t \in (0, 1] \quad (1.1)$$

with the nonlocal fractional-order integral condition

$$mx(0) + \int_0^1 h((x(\varsigma), I^{\alpha-\delta} x(\varsigma))) d\varsigma = \sum_{k=1}^m a_k x(\tau_k), \quad a_k > 0, \quad \varsigma, \delta \in (0, 1], \quad \tau_k \in [0, 1] \quad (1.2)$$

A study of the existence of solutions $x \in C[0, 1]$ to the problems (1.1) and (1.2) will be conducted, followed by the establishment of the existence of maximal and minimal solutions. Then the solution will be examined to determine whether it is unique and continuously dependent.

Following is a summary of the remainder of the paper: In Section 2, the main definitions and relations we use are described, the existence of continuous solutions to the problems (1.1) and (1.2) is demonstrated, and some properties such as the existence of at least one solution are investigated. Section 3 proves the existence of maximal and minimal solutions. It is discussed in Sections 4 and 5 that the uniqueness of the solution and its continuous dependence must satisfy certain conditions.

2. Preliminaries and Main results

The following assumptions should be considered:

(H₁) let $F_1(t, x, y)$ be a nonempty set, convex and closed for all $(t, x, y) \in [0, 1] \times R \times R$ such that

- (i) $F_1(t, x, y)$ is measurable in $t \in [0, 1]$ for every $x, y \in R$.
- (ii) $F_1(t, x, y)$ is upper semicontinuous in x and y for every $t \in [0, 1]$.

(iii) There exist a bounded measurable function $m_1 : [0, 1] \rightarrow R$ and a positive constant k_1 , such that

$$\|F(t, x, y)\| = \sup\{f_1 : f_1 \in F_1(t, x, y)\} \leq |m_1(t)| + k_1(|x| + |y|).$$

Remark 2.1 In light of the assumption (H₁), it may be possible to deduce (see[2], [?] and [12]) that there exists $f_1 \in F_1(t, x, y)$, such that

(iv) $f_1 : [0, 1] \times R \times R \rightarrow R$ is measurable in t for every $x, y \in R$ and continuous in x, y for $t \in [0, 1]$, a bounded measurable function $m_1 : [0, 1] \rightarrow R$ exists along with a positive constant $k_1 > 0$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} |f_1(t, x, y)| &\leq |m_1(t)| + k_1(|x| + |y|) \\ &\leq m_1^* + k_1(|x| + |y|), \quad m_1^* = \sup I^{1-\alpha}|m_1(t)| \end{aligned}$$

As a result, the functional f_1 satisfies the differential equation

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = f_1(t, D^\alpha x(t), D^\beta f_2(t, I^\gamma x(t))) \quad \alpha, \beta, \gamma \in (0, 1], \quad t \in (0, 1] \quad (2.1)$$

(H₂) For any $x \in R$, $f_2 : [0, 1] \times R \rightarrow R$ is measurable at t and continuous at $t \in [0, 1]$, and a bounded measurable function $m_2 : [0, 1] \rightarrow R$ and a positive constant

$k_2 > 0$ exist such that

$$\begin{aligned} |f_2(t, x)| &\leq |m_2(t)| + k_2|x| \\ &\leq m_2^* + k_2|x|, \quad m_2^* = \sup D^\beta |m_2(t)| \end{aligned}$$

(H₃) The root r_1 of the following equation is positive

$$m_1^* + \left(\frac{k_1}{\Gamma(2-\alpha)} - 1\right)r_1 + \frac{k_1 m_2^*}{\Gamma(2-\alpha)} = 0$$

(H₄) For all $x, y \in R$, $h : R \times R \rightarrow R$ is continuous in x, y for $t \in I$. It is also evident that there exists a constant $b_3 > 0$ where

$$|h(x, y)| \leq b_3(|x| + |y|)$$

Remark 2.2 As a result of (H₁), we can conclude that every solution to (1.1) is also a solution to (2.1).

Here are some definitions we should recall:

Definition 1 ([16]) Let $f \in L^1[a, b]$, $\beta \in R^+$ in terms of the the fractional integral of Riemann-Liouville, f of order β is given by

$$I_a^\beta f(t) = \int_a^t \frac{(t-s)^{\beta-1}}{\Gamma(\beta)} f(s) ds,$$

Definition 2 ([14]) The Caputo fractional-order derivative of $f(t)$ of order $\alpha \in (0, 1]$ can be expressed as follows:

$$D_a^\alpha f(t) = I_a^{1-\alpha} \frac{d}{dt} f(t) = \int_a^t \frac{(t-s)^{-\alpha}}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \frac{d}{ds} f(s) ds,$$

Now, our next step is to prove the following auxiliary result.

Lemma 2.1 *If there is a solution to problems (2.1)-(1.2), it is given in the following form*

$$x(t) = I^\alpha y(t) + \frac{1}{m} \left[\left(\sum_{k=1}^m a_k x(\tau_k) \right) - \int_0^1 h(x(\varsigma), I^{2\alpha-\delta} y(\varsigma) + \frac{x(0)}{\Gamma(\alpha-\delta+1)}) d\varsigma \right] \quad (2.2)$$

When y satisfies the equation.

$$\begin{aligned} y(t) &= \int_0^t \frac{(t-\sigma)^{-\alpha}}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} f_1(\sigma, y(\sigma)), \int_0^\sigma \frac{(\sigma-s)^{-\beta}}{\Gamma(1-\beta)} f_2'(s, \int_0^s \frac{(s-\theta)^{\gamma-1}}{\Gamma(\gamma)} (I^\alpha y(\theta) + \frac{1}{m} \left[\sum_{k=1}^m a_k x(\tau_k) \right) \\ &\quad - \int_0^1 h(x(\varsigma), I^{2\alpha-\delta} y(\varsigma) + \frac{x(0)}{\Gamma(\alpha-\delta+1)}) d\varsigma] d\theta) ds) d\sigma \end{aligned} \quad (2.3)$$

In addition, the two systems (2.1) and (1.2), and (2.2) and (2.3) are equivalent.

Proof. x is the solution to (2.1) and (1.2). Thus, we obtain

$$D^\alpha x(t) = I^{1-\alpha} \frac{dx}{dt} = I^{1-\alpha} f_1(t, D^\alpha x(t), D^\beta f_2(t, I^\gamma x(t)))$$

Assuming $D^\alpha x(t) = y(t)$,

$$\begin{aligned} y(t) &= I^{1-\alpha} f_1(t, y(t), \int_0^t \frac{(t-s)^{-\beta}}{\Gamma(1-\beta)} f_2'(s, I^\gamma x(s)) ds) \\ &= I^{1-\alpha} f_1(t, y(t), \int_0^t \frac{(t-s)^{-\beta}}{\Gamma(1-\beta)} f_2'(s, \int_0^s \frac{(s-\theta)^{\gamma-1}}{\Gamma(\gamma)} x(\theta) d\theta) ds) \end{aligned} \quad (2.4)$$

and

$$x(t) = I^\alpha y(t) + x(0) \quad (2.5)$$

Now

$$\begin{aligned} I^{\alpha-\delta} x(\varsigma) &= I^{\alpha-\delta} [I^\alpha y(\varsigma) + x(0)] \\ &= I^{2\alpha-\delta} y(\varsigma) + \frac{x(0)}{\Gamma(\alpha-\delta+1)} \end{aligned} \quad (2.6)$$

Consequently, we obtain (2.2) from (1.2) and (2.5), and from (2.2), (2.4) we obtain (2.3). By letting $y(t) = D^\alpha x(t)$ in (2.2), we obtain (1.2), and in (2.3) we obtain

$$I^{1-\alpha} \frac{d}{dt} x(t) = I^{1-\alpha} f_1(t, D^\alpha x(t), \int_0^t \frac{(t-s)^{-\beta}}{\Gamma(1-\beta)} f_2'(s, I^\gamma x(s)) ds)$$

As a result of operating by I^α , and then by $\frac{d}{dt}$, respectively, we obtain (2.1).

Therefore, the two systems (2.1) and (1.2), as well as (2.2) and (2.3), are equivalent.

Theorem 2.1 *If the conditions (H_1) - (H_4) hold, then problems (1.2) and (2.1) have a solution in $C(I)$.*

Proof. A closed ball Q_{r_1} and an operator F_1 are characterized as follows:

$$Q_{r_1} = \{y \in C(I) : \|y\| \leq r_1\}, \quad r_1 = m_1^* + \frac{k_1(r_1 + m_2^*)}{\Gamma(2-\alpha)}$$

and

$$F_1 y(t) = I^{1-\alpha} f_1(t, y(t), \int_0^t \frac{(t-s)^{-\beta}}{\Gamma(1-\beta)} f_2'(s, \int_0^s \frac{(s-\theta)^{\gamma-1}}{\Gamma(\gamma)} x(\theta) d\theta) ds)$$

Accordingly, for $y \in Q_{r_1}$

$$\begin{aligned} |F_1 y(t)| &= \left| \int_0^t \frac{(t-\varsigma)^{-\alpha}}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} f_1(\varsigma, y(\varsigma), D^\beta f_2(\varsigma, I^\gamma x(\varsigma))) d\varsigma \right| \\ &\leq \int_0^t \frac{(t-\varsigma)^{-\alpha}}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} [m_1 + k_1(|y(\varsigma)| + |D^\beta f_2(\varsigma, I^\gamma x(\varsigma))|)] d\varsigma \\ &\leq \int_0^t \frac{(t-\varsigma)^{-\alpha}}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} [m_1 + k_1\|y\| + k_1 D^\beta |f_2(\varsigma, I^\gamma x(\varsigma))|] d\varsigma \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&\leq \int_0^t \frac{(t-\varsigma)^{-\alpha}}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} [m_1 + k_1 r_1 + k_1 D^\beta |m_2(\varsigma)| + k_1 D^\beta k_2 \int_0^\varsigma \frac{(\varsigma-s)^{\gamma-1}}{\Gamma(\gamma)} |x(s)| ds] \\
&\leq \int_0^t \frac{(t-\varsigma)^{-\alpha}}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} [m_1 + k_1 r_1 + k_1 m_2^* + k_1 D^\beta k_2 I^\gamma |x(\varsigma)|] d\varsigma \\
&\leq \int_0^t \frac{(t-\varsigma)^{-\alpha}}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} [m_1 + k_1 r_1 + k_1 m_2^* + k_1 D^\beta k_2 I^\gamma \|x\|] d\varsigma \\
&\leq \int_0^t \frac{(t-\varsigma)^{-\alpha}}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} [m_1 + k_1 r_1 + k_1 m_2^*] d\varsigma \\
&\leq m_1^* + \frac{k_1}{\Gamma(2-\alpha)} [r_1 + m_2^*] = r_1
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore, we have

$$\|F_1 y\| \leq m_1^* + \frac{k_1}{\Gamma(2-\alpha)} [r_1 + m_2^*] = r_1$$

Consequently, $F_1 : Q_{r_1} \rightarrow Q_{r_1}$ and the family $\{F_1 y\}$ is uniformly bound on Q_{r_1} . Let $y \in Q_{r_1}$ and $t_1, t_2 \in I$, where $t_2 > t_1$ and $|t_1 - t_2| < \delta$, therefore,

$$\begin{aligned}
|F_1 y(t_2) - F_1 y(t_1)| &= \left| \int_0^{t_2} \frac{(t_2-\sigma)^{-\alpha}}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} f_1(\sigma, y(\sigma), \int_0^\sigma \frac{(\sigma-s)^{-\beta}}{\Gamma(1-\beta)} f_2'(s, I^\gamma x(s)) ds) d\sigma \right. \\
&\quad \left. - \int_0^{t_1} \frac{(t_1-\sigma)^{-\alpha}}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} f_1(\sigma, y(\sigma), \int_0^\sigma \frac{(\sigma-s)^{-\beta}}{\Gamma(1-\beta)} f_2'(s, I^\gamma x(s)) ds) d\sigma \right| \\
&= \left| \int_0^{t_2} \frac{(t_2-\sigma)^{-\alpha}}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} f_1(\sigma, y(\sigma), \int_0^\sigma \frac{(\sigma-s)^{-\beta}}{\Gamma(1-\beta)} f_2'(s, I^\gamma x(s)) ds) d\sigma \right. \\
&\quad \left. - \int_0^{t_1} \frac{(t_2-\sigma)^{-\alpha}}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} f_1(\sigma, y(\sigma), \int_0^\sigma \frac{(\sigma-s)^{-\beta}}{\Gamma(1-\beta)} f_2'(s, I^\gamma x(s)) ds) d\sigma \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \int_0^{t_1} \frac{(t_2-\sigma)^{-\alpha}}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} f_1(\sigma, y(\sigma), \int_0^\sigma \frac{(\sigma-s)^{-\beta}}{\Gamma(1-\beta)} f_2'(s, I^\gamma x(s)) ds) d\sigma \right. \\
&\quad \left. - \int_0^{t_1} \frac{(t_1-\sigma)^{-\alpha}}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} f_1(\sigma, y(\sigma), \int_0^\sigma \frac{(\sigma-s)^{-\beta}}{\Gamma(1-\beta)} f_2'(s, I^\gamma x(s)) ds) d\sigma \right| \\
&\leq \int_{t_1}^{t_2} \frac{(t_2-\sigma)^{-\alpha}}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} |f_1(\sigma, y(\sigma), \int_0^\sigma \frac{(\sigma-s)^{-\beta}}{\Gamma(1-\beta)} f_2'(s, I^\gamma x(s)) ds)| d\sigma \\
&\quad + \int_0^{t_1} \frac{(t_2-\sigma)^{-\alpha} - (t_1-\sigma)^{-\alpha}}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} |f_1(\sigma, y(\sigma), \int_0^\sigma \frac{(\sigma-s)^{-\beta}}{\Gamma(1-\beta)} f_2'(s, I^\gamma x(s)) ds)| d\sigma \\
&\leq \int_{t_1}^{t_2} \frac{(t_2-\sigma)^{-\alpha}}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} |f_1(\sigma, y(\sigma), \int_0^\sigma \frac{(\sigma-s)^{-\beta}}{\Gamma(1-\beta)} f_2'(s, I^\gamma x(s)) ds)| d\sigma \\
&\quad + \int_0^{t_1} \frac{(t_2-\sigma)^\alpha - (t_1-\sigma)^\alpha}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)(t_2-\sigma)^\alpha(t_1-\sigma)^\alpha} |f_1(\sigma, y(\sigma), \int_0^\sigma \frac{(\sigma-s)^{-\beta}}{\Gamma(1-\beta)} f_2'(s, I^\gamma x(s)) ds)| d\sigma
\end{aligned}$$

The Arzela–Ascoli Theorem [10] indicates that mapping F_1 is relatively compact when family $\{F_1 y\}$ is equi-continuous on Q_{r_1} .

Let $\{y_n\} \subset Q_{r_1}$ form a convergent sequence such that $y_n \rightarrow y$; then,

$$F_1 y_n(t) = \int_0^t \frac{(t-\sigma)^{-\alpha}}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} f_1(\sigma, y_n(\sigma), \int_0^\sigma \frac{(\sigma-s)^{-\beta}}{\Gamma(1-\beta)} f_2'(s, \int_0^s \frac{(s-\theta)^{\gamma-1}}{\Gamma(\gamma)} x(\theta) d\theta) ds) d\sigma$$

According to the Lebesgue-dominated convergence Theorem [10],

$$\begin{aligned}
\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Fy_n(t) &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_0^t \frac{(t-\sigma)^{-\alpha}}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} f_1(\sigma, y_n(\sigma), \int_0^\sigma \frac{(\sigma-s)^{-\beta}}{\Gamma(1-\beta)} f_2'(s, \int_0^s \frac{(s-\theta)^{\gamma-1}}{\Gamma(\gamma)} x(\theta) d\theta) ds) d\sigma \\
&= \int_0^t \frac{(t-\sigma)^{-\alpha}}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} f_1(\sigma, \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} y_n(\sigma), \int_0^\sigma \frac{(\sigma-s)^{-\beta}}{\Gamma(1-\beta)} f_2'(s, \int_0^s \frac{(s-\theta)^{\gamma-1}}{\Gamma(\gamma)} x(\theta) d\theta) ds) d\sigma \\
&= \int_0^t \frac{(t-\sigma)^{-\alpha}}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} f_1(\sigma, y(\sigma), \int_0^\sigma \frac{(\sigma-s)^{-\beta}}{\Gamma(1-\beta)} f_2'(s, \int_0^s \frac{(s-\theta)^{\gamma-1}}{\Gamma(\gamma)} x(\theta) d\theta) ds) d\sigma \\
&= Fy(t)
\end{aligned}$$

Consequently, $F_1 : Q_{r_1} \rightarrow Q_{r_1}$ is continuous, and there exists at least one solution $y \in C[0, 1]$ of (2.3) according to Schauder's Fixed Point Theorem [10]. Now

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{dx}{dt} &= \frac{d}{dt} \left[x(0) + I^\alpha y(t) \right] \\
&= \frac{d}{dt} I^\alpha I^{1-\alpha} f_1(t, D^\alpha x(t), D^\beta f_2(t, I^\gamma x(t))) \\
&= \frac{d}{dt} I f_1(t, D^\alpha x(t), D^\beta f_2(t, I^\gamma x(t))) \\
&= f_1(t, D^\alpha x(t), D^\beta f_2(t, I^\gamma x(t)))
\end{aligned}$$

Using (2.2), (2.6), we obtain,

$$\begin{aligned}
x(t) &= I^\alpha y(t) + \frac{1}{m} \left[\left(\sum_{k=1}^m a_k x(\tau_k) \right) - \int_0^1 h(x(\varsigma), I^{2\alpha-\delta} y(\varsigma) + \frac{x(0)}{\Gamma(\alpha-\sigma+1)}) d\varsigma \right] \\
&= I^\alpha y(t) + \frac{1}{m} \left[\left(\sum_{k=1}^m a_k x(\tau_k) \right) - \int_0^1 h(x(\varsigma), I^{\alpha-\delta} x(\varsigma)) d\varsigma \right] \tag{2.7}
\end{aligned}$$

Substituting (2.5) in (2.7), we obtain

$$mx(0) + \int_0^1 h(x(\varsigma), I^{\alpha-\delta} x(\varsigma)) d\varsigma = \sum_{k=1}^m a_k x(\tau_k)$$

Thus, problems (2.1)- (1.2) and integral equation (2.3) are equivalent. Accordingly, there must be at least one solution $y \in C[0, 1]$ to problems (2.1)- (1.2).

Theorem 2.2 *If (H_1) - (H_4) are satisfied, then for a fixed function y (given by Theorem 1), $\exists x \in C(I)$ and satisfies (2.2).*

Proof. Assume that Q_{r_2} represents a closed ball

$$Q_{r_2} = \{x \in C(I) : \|x\| \leq r_2\},$$

$$r_2 = \frac{A + \frac{b_3}{m} \left[\frac{r_1}{\Gamma(2\alpha-\delta+1)} + \frac{x(0)}{\Gamma(\alpha-\delta+1)} + \frac{r_1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} \right]}{\left(1 - \frac{b_3}{m}\right)}, \quad A = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{k=1}^m a_k x(\tau_k),$$

Defining operator F_2

$$F_2 x(t) = \frac{1}{m} \left[\sum_{k=1}^m a_k x(\tau_k) - \int_0^1 h(x(\varsigma), I^{2\alpha-\delta} y(\varsigma) + \frac{x(0)}{\Gamma(\alpha-\delta+1)}) d\varsigma \right] + I^\alpha y(t)$$

Let $x \in Q_{r_2}$, then

$$\begin{aligned}
|F_2x(t)| &= \left| \frac{1}{m} \left[\sum_{k=1}^m a_k x(\tau_k) - \int_0^1 h(x(\varsigma), I^{2\alpha-\delta}y(\varsigma) + \frac{x(0)}{\Gamma(\alpha-\delta+1)})d\varsigma \right] + I^\alpha y(t) \right| \\
&\leq \frac{1}{m} \sum_{k=1}^m a_k x(\tau_k) + \frac{1}{m} \int_0^1 |h(x(\varsigma), I^{2\alpha-\delta}y(\varsigma) + \frac{x(0)}{\Gamma(\alpha-\delta+1)})|d\varsigma + I^\alpha |y(t)| \\
&\leq A + \frac{1}{m} \int_0^1 |b_3(|x(\varsigma)| + |I^{2\alpha-\delta}y(\varsigma) + \frac{x(0)}{\Gamma(\alpha-\delta+1)})|d\varsigma + \frac{\|y\|}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} \\
&\leq A + \frac{b_3}{m} \left[r_2 + \frac{r_1}{\Gamma(2\alpha-\delta+1)} + \frac{x(0)}{\Gamma(\alpha-\delta+1)} \right] + \frac{r_1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} = r_2
\end{aligned}$$

and

$$\|F_2x(t)\| \leq A + \frac{b_3}{m} \left[r_2 + \frac{r_1}{\Gamma(2\alpha-\delta+1)} + \frac{x(0)}{\Gamma(\alpha-\delta+1)} \right] + \frac{r_1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} = r_2$$

In the same manner as was performed above, $F_2 : Q_{r_2} \rightarrow Q_{r_2}$ and $\{F_2x\}$ are uniformly bound by Q_{r_2} .

Consider $x \in Q_{r_2}$ and $t_1, t_2 \in I$; furthermore, consider $t_2 > t_1$ and $|t_1 - t_2| \leq \delta$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned}
|F_2x(t_2) - F_2x(t_1)| &= \left| \frac{1}{m} \sum_{k=1}^m a_k x(\tau_k) - \frac{1}{m} \int_0^1 h(x(\varsigma), I^{2\alpha-\delta}y(\varsigma) + \frac{x(0)}{\Gamma(\alpha-\delta+1)})d\varsigma + I^\alpha y(t_2) \right. \\
&\quad \left. - \frac{1}{m} \sum_{k=1}^m a_k x(\tau_k) + \frac{1}{m} \int_0^1 h(x(\varsigma), I^{2\alpha-\delta}y(\varsigma) + \frac{x(0)}{\Gamma(\alpha-\delta+1)})d\varsigma - I^\alpha y(t_1) \right| \\
&\leq \int_0^{t_2} |f_1(\varsigma, y(\varsigma), D^\beta f_2(t, I^\gamma x(\varsigma)))|d\varsigma - \int_0^{t_1} |f_1(\varsigma, y(\varsigma), D^\beta f_2(t, I^\gamma x(\varsigma)))|d\varsigma \\
&\leq \int_{t_1}^{t_2} |f_1(\varsigma, y(\varsigma), D^\beta f_2(t, I^\gamma x(\varsigma)))|d\varsigma
\end{aligned}$$

Consequently, the family $\{F_2x\}$ is equicontinuous on Q_{r_2} , and the operator F_2 is relatively compact.

Taking into account $\{x_n\} \in Q_{r_2}$ and $x_n \rightarrow x$; then,

$$F_2x_n(t) = I^\alpha y(t) + \frac{1}{m} \left[\sum_{k=1}^m a_k x(\tau_k) - \int_0^1 h(x_n(\varsigma), I^{2\alpha-\delta}y(\varsigma) + \frac{x(0)}{\Gamma(\alpha-\delta+1)})d\varsigma \right]$$

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} F_2x_n(t) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left(I^\alpha y(t) + \frac{1}{m} \left[\sum_{k=1}^m a_k x(\tau_k) - \int_0^1 h(x_n(\varsigma), I^{2\alpha-\delta}y(\varsigma) + \frac{x(0)}{\Gamma(\alpha-\delta+1)})d\varsigma \right] \right)$$

To establish convergence, we use the Lebesgue-dominated convergence theorem.

$$\begin{aligned}
\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} F_2x_n(t) &= I^\alpha y(t) + \frac{1}{m} \left[\sum_{k=1}^m a_k x(\tau_k) - \int_0^1 h(\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} x_n(\varsigma), I^{2\alpha-\delta}y(\varsigma) + \frac{x(0)}{\Gamma(\alpha-\delta+1)})d\varsigma \right] \\
&= I^\alpha y(t) + \frac{1}{m} \left[\sum_{k=1}^m a_k x(\tau_k) - \int_0^1 h(x(\varsigma), I^{2\alpha-\delta}y(\varsigma) + \frac{x(0)}{\Gamma(\alpha-\delta+1)})d\varsigma \right] \\
&= F_2x(t)
\end{aligned}$$

As a result, $F_2 x_n(t) \rightarrow F_2 x(t)$. It follows that operator F_2 is continuous, and there exists $x \in Q_{r_2} \subset C(I)$ that satisfies (2.2).

3. Maximal and Minimal Solutions

Lemma 3.2 *Consider the case in which Theorem (2.1) holds. Let $x, y \in C(I)$ satisfy*

$$x(t) \leq \int_0^t \frac{(t-\sigma)^{-\alpha}}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} f_1(\sigma, x(\sigma), \int_0^\sigma \frac{(\sigma-s)^{-\beta}}{\Gamma(1-\beta)} f_2'(s, \int_0^s \frac{(s-\theta)^{\gamma-1}}{\Gamma(\gamma)} [I^\alpha x(\theta) + x(0)] d\theta) ds) d\sigma$$

$$y(t) \geq \int_0^t \frac{(t-\sigma)^{-\alpha}}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} f_1(\sigma, y(\sigma), \int_0^\sigma \frac{(\sigma-s)^{-\beta}}{\Gamma(1-\beta)} f_2'(s, \int_0^s \frac{(s-\theta)^{\gamma-1}}{\Gamma(\gamma)} [I^\alpha y(\theta) + x(0)] d\theta) ds) d\sigma$$

One of them must be strict.

let f_1 and f_2 be monotonic non-decreasing functions; hence,

$$x(t) < y(t), \quad t > 0 \tag{3.1}$$

Proof. Considering (3.1) to be false, then $\exists t_1$ such that

$$x(t_1) = y(t_1), \quad t_1 > 0, \quad x(t) < y(t), \quad 0 < t < t_1$$

Considering the monotonicity of f_1 and f_2 , we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} x(t_1) &\leq \int_0^{t_1} \frac{(t_1-\sigma)^{-\alpha}}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} f_1(\sigma, x(\sigma), \int_0^\sigma \frac{(\sigma-s)^{-\beta}}{\Gamma(1-\beta)} f_2'(s, \int_0^s \frac{(s-\theta)^{\gamma-1}}{\Gamma(\gamma)} [I^\alpha x(\theta) + x(0)] d\theta) ds) d\sigma \\ &< \int_0^{t_1} \frac{(t_1-\sigma)^{-\alpha}}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} f_1(\sigma, y(\sigma), \int_0^\sigma \frac{(\sigma-s)^{-\beta}}{\Gamma(1-\beta)} f_2'(s, \int_0^s \frac{(s-\theta)^{\gamma-1}}{\Gamma(\gamma)} [I^\alpha y(\theta) + x(0)] d\theta) ds) d\sigma \\ &< y(t_1) \end{aligned}$$

Thus, $x(t_1) < y(t_1)$, which contradicts $x(t_1) = y(t_1)$; therefore, $x(t) < y(t)$, $t \in I$.

Theorem 3.3 *Assume that the conditions in Theorem (2.1) are met. The maximum and minimal solutions to problems (1.2) and (2.1) are determined by the monotonic non-decreasing functions f_1 and f_2 .*

Proof. In order to know whether there is a maximal solution to Equation (2.3), we take $\varepsilon > 0$ and consider the following integral equations:

$$y_\varepsilon(t) = I^{1-\alpha} f_{1\varepsilon}(t, y_\varepsilon(t), \int_0^t \frac{(t-s)^{-\beta}}{\Gamma(1-\beta)} f_{2\varepsilon}'(s, \int_0^s \frac{(s-\theta)^{\gamma-1}}{\Gamma(\gamma)} [x(0) + I^\alpha y_\varepsilon(\theta)] d\theta) ds) \tag{3.2}$$

where

$$f_{1\varepsilon}(s, x_\varepsilon(s), y_\varepsilon(s)) = f_1(s, x_\varepsilon(s), y_\varepsilon(s)) + \varepsilon$$

$$f_{2\varepsilon}(s, x_\varepsilon(s)) = f_2(s, x_\varepsilon(s)) + \varepsilon$$

According to Theorem (2.1), equation (3.2) has a continuous solution y_ε since f_1 and f_2 satisfy the assumptions of Theorem (2.1).

$$\begin{aligned} y_\varepsilon(t) &= \int_0^t \frac{(t-\sigma)^{-\alpha}}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} [\varepsilon + f_1(\sigma, y_\varepsilon(\sigma), \int_0^\sigma \frac{(\sigma-s)^{-\beta}}{\Gamma(1-\beta)} \{ \varepsilon + f_2'(s, \int_0^s \frac{(s-\theta)^{\gamma-1}}{\Gamma(\gamma)} x(0) d\theta \\ &+ \int_0^s \frac{(s-\theta)^{\gamma-1}}{\Gamma(\gamma)} I^\alpha y_\varepsilon(\theta) d\theta \} ds)] d\sigma \end{aligned}$$

Taking $\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2 > 0$ as $0 < \varepsilon_2 < \varepsilon_1 < \varepsilon$ then, we can state:

$$\begin{aligned} y_{\varepsilon_1}(t) &= \int_0^t \frac{(t-\sigma)^{-\alpha}}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} [\varepsilon_1 + f_1(\sigma, y_{\varepsilon_1}(\sigma), \int_0^\sigma \frac{(\sigma-s)^{-\beta}}{\Gamma(1-\beta)} \{ \varepsilon_1 + f_2'(s, \int_0^s \frac{(s-\theta)^{\gamma-1}}{\Gamma(\gamma)} x(0) d\theta \\ &+ \int_0^s \frac{(s-\theta)^{\gamma-1}}{\Gamma(\gamma)} I^\alpha y_{\varepsilon_1}(\theta) d\theta \} ds)] d\sigma \\ &> \int_0^t \frac{(t-\sigma)^{-\alpha}}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} [\varepsilon_2 + f_1(\sigma, y_{\varepsilon_1}(\sigma), \int_0^\sigma \frac{(\sigma-s)^{-\beta}}{\Gamma(1-\beta)} \{ \varepsilon_2 + f_2'(s, \int_0^s \frac{(s-\theta)^{\gamma-1}}{\Gamma(\gamma)} x(0) d\theta \\ &+ \int_0^s \frac{(s-\theta)^{\gamma-1}}{\Gamma(\gamma)} I^\alpha y_{\varepsilon_1}(\theta) d\theta \} ds)] d\sigma \end{aligned} \tag{3.3}$$

$$\begin{aligned} y_{\varepsilon_2}(t) &= \int_0^t \frac{(t-\sigma)^{-\alpha}}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} [\varepsilon_2 + f_1(\sigma, y_{\varepsilon_2}(\sigma), \int_0^\sigma \frac{(\sigma-s)^{-\beta}}{\Gamma(1-\beta)} \{ \varepsilon_2 + f_2'(s, \int_0^s \frac{(s-\theta)^{\gamma-1}}{\Gamma(\gamma)} x(0) d\theta \\ &+ \int_0^s \frac{(s-\theta)^{\gamma-1}}{\Gamma(\gamma)} I^\alpha y_{\varepsilon_2}(\theta) d\theta \} ds)] d\sigma \end{aligned} \tag{3.4}$$

Lemma (3.2) is applied to estimates (3.3) and (3.4), resulting in

$$y_{\varepsilon_2} < y_{\varepsilon_1}, \quad t \in [0, 1]$$

Theorem (2.1) proves that $y_\varepsilon(t)$ is uniformly bounded on I , and that a decreasing sequence ε_n exists by Arzela's Theorem. such that $\varepsilon_n \rightarrow 0$, $n \rightarrow \infty$, and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} y_{\varepsilon_n}(t)$ exists uniformly in I , and this limit is represented by $r(t)$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^t \frac{(t-\sigma)^{-\alpha}}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} f_1(\sigma, y_{\varepsilon_n}(\sigma), \int_0^\sigma \frac{(\sigma-s)^{-\beta}}{\Gamma(1-\beta)} f_2'(s, \int_0^s \frac{(s-\theta)^{\gamma-1}}{\Gamma(\gamma)} [I^\alpha y_{\varepsilon_n}(\theta) + x(0)] d\theta) ds) d\sigma \rightarrow \\ \int_0^t \frac{(t-\sigma)^{-\alpha}}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} f_1(\sigma, r(\sigma), \int_0^\sigma \frac{(\sigma-s)^{-\beta}}{\Gamma(1-\beta)} f_2'(s, \int_0^s \frac{(s-\theta)^{\gamma-1}}{\Gamma(\gamma)} [I^\alpha r(\theta) + x(0)] d\theta) ds) d\sigma \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} r(t) &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} y_{\varepsilon_n}(t) \\ &= \int_0^t \frac{(t-\sigma)^{-\alpha}}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} f_1(\sigma, r(\sigma), \int_0^\sigma \frac{(\sigma-s)^{-\beta}}{\Gamma(1-\beta)} f_2'(s, \int_0^s \frac{(s-\theta)^{\gamma-1}}{\Gamma(\gamma)} [I^\alpha r(\theta) + x(0)] d\theta) ds) d\sigma \end{aligned}$$

This leads to the conclusion that $r(t)$ is a solution to (2.3).

Lastly, we will demonstrate that $r(t)$ is the maximal solution to the equation (2.3).

Here, let's consider $y(t)$ any solution to (2.3), and then

$$y(t) = \int_0^t \frac{(t-\sigma)^{-\alpha}}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} f_1(\sigma, y(\sigma), \int_0^\sigma \frac{(\sigma-s)^{-\beta}}{\Gamma(1-\beta)} f_2'(s, \int_0^s \frac{(s-\theta)^{\gamma-1}}{\Gamma(\gamma)} [I^\alpha y(\theta) + x(0)] d\theta) ds) d\sigma \quad (3.5)$$

also

$$\begin{aligned} y_\varepsilon(t) &= \int_0^t \frac{(t-\sigma)^{-\alpha}}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} [\varepsilon + f_1(\sigma, y_\varepsilon(\sigma), \int_0^\sigma \frac{(\sigma-s)^{-\beta}}{\Gamma(1-\beta)} \{ \varepsilon \\ &+ f_2'(s, \int_0^s \frac{(s-\theta)^{\gamma-1}}{\Gamma(\gamma)} [I^\alpha y_\varepsilon(\theta) + x(0)] d\theta \}) ds)] d\sigma \\ &> \int_0^t \frac{(t-\sigma)^{-\alpha}}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} f_1(\sigma, y_\varepsilon(\sigma), \int_0^\sigma \frac{(\sigma-s)^{-\beta}}{\Gamma(1-\beta)} f_2'(s, \int_0^s \frac{(s-\theta)^{\gamma-1}}{\Gamma(\gamma)} [I^\alpha y_\varepsilon(\theta) + x(0)] d\theta) ds) d\sigma \end{aligned} \quad (3.6)$$

By applying Lemma (3.2) to estimates (3.5) and (3.6), we obtain

$$y(t) < y_\varepsilon(t), \quad t \in I.$$

Based on the uniqueness of the maximal solution. It is evident that $y_\varepsilon(t)$ tends to $r(t)$ uniformly on I as $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$.

The existence of minimal solutions can also be established in the same manner as above.

4. Uniqueness of the Solution

Assume the following conditions:

- (i*) A positive constant k_1 ensures that $f_1 : [0, 1] \times R \times R \rightarrow R$ can be measured in $t \in [0, 1]$ for every $x, y \in R$ and satisfies the Lipschitz condition such that see ([?],[?])

$$|f_1(t, x_1, y_1) - f_1(t, x_2, y_2)| \leq K_1(|x_1 - x_2| + |y_1 - y_2|)$$

From that we have

$$|f_1(t, x, y)| \leq |f_1(t, 0, 0)| + K_1(|x| + |y|)$$

then

$$|f_1(t, x, y)| \leq m_1 + K_1(|x| + |y|)$$

where $m_1 = \sup_{t \in I} |f_1(t, 0, 0)|$

- (ii*) A measurable function $f_2' : [0, 1] \times R \rightarrow R$ is given in $t \in [0, 1]$ and satisfies Lipschitz's condition with a positive constant k_2 , such that

$$|f_2'(t, y_1) - f_2'(t, y_2)| \leq K_2(|y_1 - y_2|)$$

And that implies

$$|f_2'(t, y)| \leq |f_2'(t, 0)| + K_2|y|$$

then

$$|f_2'(t, y)| \leq m_2 + K_2|y|$$

where $m_2 = \sup_{t \in I} |f_2'(t, 0)|$

(iii*) For every $x, y \in R$, $h : R \times R \rightarrow R$ satisfies the Lipschitz condition with $b_3 > 0$ as the Lipschitz constant.

$$|h(x_1, y_1) - h(x_2, y_2)| \leq b_3(|x_1 - x_2| + |y_1 - y_2|)$$

Theorem 4.4 Assume that assumptions (i*) – (iii*) are satisfied if

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{k_1}{\Gamma(2-\alpha)} + \frac{k_1 k_2}{\Gamma(2-\alpha)\Gamma(\alpha+1)\Gamma(\gamma+1)\Gamma(2-\beta)} \\ + \frac{k_1 k_2}{\Gamma(2-\alpha)\Gamma(2\alpha-\sigma+1)\Gamma(\gamma+1)\Gamma(2-\beta)} < 1 \end{aligned}$$

then we have a unique solution to problem (2.3).

Proof. Assume that y_1, y_2 are two solutions to (2.3)., where

$$\begin{aligned} |y_1(t) - y_2(t)| &= \left| \int_0^t \frac{(t-\sigma)^{-\alpha}}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} f_1(\sigma, y_1(\sigma), \int_0^\sigma \frac{(\sigma-s)^{-\beta}}{\Gamma(1-\beta)} f_2'(s, \int_0^s \frac{(s-\theta)^{\gamma-1}}{\Gamma(\gamma)} (I^\alpha y_1(\theta)) \right. \\ &+ \frac{1}{m} \left[\sum_{k=1}^m a_k x(\tau_k) - \int_0^1 h(x(\varsigma), I^{2\alpha-\delta} y_1(\varsigma) + \frac{x(0)}{\Gamma(\alpha-\delta+1)}) d\varsigma d\theta \right] ds d\sigma \\ &- \int_0^t \frac{(t-\sigma)^{-\alpha}}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} f_1(\sigma, y_2(\sigma), \int_0^\sigma \frac{(\sigma-s)^{-\beta}}{\Gamma(1-\beta)} f_2'(s, \int_0^s \frac{(s-\theta)^{\gamma-1}}{\Gamma(\gamma)} (I^\alpha y_2(\theta)) \\ &+ \frac{1}{m} \left[\sum_{k=1}^m a_k x(\tau_k) - \int_0^1 h(x(\varsigma), I^{2\alpha-\delta} y_2(\varsigma) + \frac{x(0)}{\Gamma(\alpha-\delta+1)}) d\varsigma d\theta \right] ds d\sigma \left. \right| \\ &\leq \int_0^t \frac{(t-\sigma)^{-\alpha}}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \left[k_1(|y_1(\sigma)| + \int_0^\sigma \frac{(\sigma-s)^{-\beta}}{\Gamma(1-\beta)} |f_2'(s, \int_0^s \frac{(s-\theta)^{\gamma-1}}{\Gamma(\gamma)} \right. \\ &\cdot [I^\alpha y_1(\theta) + \frac{1}{m} \left[\sum_{k=1}^m a_k x(\tau_k) - \int_0^1 h(x(\varsigma), I^{2\alpha-\delta} y_1(\varsigma) + \frac{x(0)}{\Gamma(\alpha-\delta+1)}) d\varsigma \right] d\theta) ds) | d\sigma \\ &- \int_0^t \frac{(t-\sigma)^{-\alpha}}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \left[k_1(|y_2(\sigma)| + \int_0^\sigma \frac{(\sigma-s)^{-\beta}}{\Gamma(1-\beta)} |f_2'(s, \int_0^s \frac{(s-\theta)^{\gamma-1}}{\Gamma(\gamma)} \right. \\ &\cdot [I^\alpha y_2(\theta) + \frac{1}{m} \left[\sum_{k=1}^m a_k x(\tau_k) - \int_0^1 h(x(\varsigma), I^{2\alpha-\delta} y_2(\varsigma) + \frac{x(0)}{\Gamma(\alpha-\delta+1)}) d\varsigma \right] d\theta) ds) | d\sigma \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&\leq \int_0^t \frac{(t-\sigma)^{-\alpha}}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} [k_1 \|y_1 - y_2\| + k_1 \int_0^\sigma \frac{(\sigma-s)^{-\beta}}{\Gamma(1-\beta)} |f'_2(s, \int_0^s \frac{(s-\theta)^{\gamma-1}}{\Gamma(\gamma)} \\
&\quad \cdot [I^\alpha y_1(\theta) + \frac{1}{m} [\sum_{k=1}^m a_k x(\tau_k) - \int_0^1 h(x(\varsigma), I^{2\alpha-\delta} y_1(\varsigma) + \frac{x(0)}{\Gamma(\alpha-\delta+1)}) d\varsigma] d\theta) ds] d\sigma \\
&\quad - f'_2(s, \int_0^s \frac{(s-\theta)^{\gamma-1}}{\Gamma(\gamma)} [I^\alpha y_2(\theta) + \frac{1}{m} [\sum_{k=1}^m a_k x(\tau_k) - \int_0^1 h(x(\varsigma), I^{2\alpha-\delta} y_2(\varsigma) \\
&\quad + \frac{x(0)}{\Gamma(\alpha-\delta+1)}) d\varsigma] d\theta) ds] d\sigma \\
&\leq \int_0^t \frac{(t-\sigma)^{-\alpha}}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} [k_1 \|y_1 - y_2\| + k_1 \int_0^\sigma \frac{(\sigma-s)^{-\beta}}{\Gamma(1-\beta)} (k_2 \int_0^s \frac{(s-\theta)^{\gamma-1}}{\Gamma(\gamma)} \\
&\quad \cdot [\frac{\|y_1\|}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} + \frac{1}{m} \sum_{k=1}^m a_k x(\tau_k) - \frac{1}{m} \int_0^1 |h(x(\varsigma), \frac{\|y_1\|}{\Gamma(2\alpha-\delta+1)} \\
&\quad + \frac{x(0)}{\Gamma(\alpha-\delta+1)})| d\varsigma] d\theta) ds \\
&\quad - (k_2 \int_0^s \frac{(s-\theta)^{\gamma-1}}{\Gamma(\gamma)} [\frac{\|y_2\|}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} + \frac{1}{m} \sum_{k=1}^m a_k x(\tau_k) \\
&\quad - \frac{1}{m} \int_0^1 |h(x(\varsigma), \frac{\|y_2\|}{\Gamma(2\alpha-\delta+1)} + \frac{x(0)}{\Gamma(2\alpha-\delta+1)})| d\varsigma] d\theta) ds] d\sigma \\
&\leq \int_0^t \frac{(t-\sigma)^{-\alpha}}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} [k_1 \|y_1 - y_2\| + k_1 \int_0^\sigma \frac{(\sigma-s)^{-\beta}}{\Gamma(1-\beta)} (k_2 \int_0^s \frac{(s-\theta)^{\gamma-1}}{\Gamma(\gamma)} \\
&\quad \cdot [\frac{\|y_1\|}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} - \frac{b_3}{m} (r_2 + \frac{\|y_1\|}{\Gamma(2\alpha-\delta+1)} + \frac{x(0)}{\Gamma(\alpha-\delta+1)}) d\theta) ds] \\
&\quad - k_2 \int_0^s \frac{(s-\theta)^{\gamma-1}}{\Gamma(\gamma)} [\frac{\|y_2\|}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} - \frac{b_3}{m} (r_2 + \frac{\|y_2\|}{\Gamma(2\alpha-\delta+1)} + \frac{x(0)}{\Gamma(\alpha-\delta+1)}) d\theta) ds] d\sigma \\
&\leq \frac{1}{\Gamma(2-\alpha)} [k_1 \|y_1 - y_2\| + \frac{k_1 k_2 \|y_1 - y_2\|}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)\Gamma(\gamma+1)\Gamma(2-\beta)} \\
&\quad + \frac{k_1 k_2 \|y_2 - y_1\|}{\Gamma(2\alpha-\delta+1)\Gamma(\gamma+1)\Gamma(2-\beta)}]
\end{aligned}$$

Hence

$$\begin{aligned}
&\|y_1 - y_2\| [1 - (\frac{k_1}{\Gamma(2-\alpha)} + \frac{k_1 k_2}{\Gamma(2-\alpha)\Gamma(\alpha+1)\Gamma(\gamma+1)\Gamma(2-\beta)} \\
&\quad + \frac{k_1 k_2}{\Gamma(2-\alpha)\Gamma(2\alpha-\delta+1)\Gamma(\gamma+1)\Gamma(2-\beta)})] \leq 0
\end{aligned}$$

This implies that the solution to (2.3) is unique.

Corollary 1 Assume that $\frac{1}{m} \sum_{k=1}^m a_k + \frac{b_3}{m} < 1$ and Theorem (4.4) is verified, then for every solution $y \in C(I)$ of equation (2.3), there is a unique solution x of equation (2.2).

Proof. Let $y \in C(I)$ and x_1, x_2 satisfy

$$\begin{aligned}
|x_2(t) - x_1(t)| &= |I^\alpha y(t) + \frac{1}{m} [(\sum_{k=1}^m a_k x_2(\tau_k)) - \int_0^1 h(x_2(\varsigma), I^{2\alpha-\delta} y(\varsigma) + \frac{x(0)}{\Gamma(\alpha-\delta+1)})] d\varsigma \\
&\quad - I^\alpha y(t) - \frac{1}{m} [(\sum_{k=1}^m a_k x_1(\tau_k)) - \int_0^1 h(x_1(\varsigma), I^{2\alpha-\delta} y(\varsigma) + \frac{x(0)}{\Gamma(\alpha-\delta+1)})] d\varsigma| \\
&\leq \frac{1}{m} [(\sum_{k=1}^m a_k |x_1(\tau_k)| - \sum_{k=1}^m a_k |x_2(\tau_k)|)] - \frac{1}{m} \int_0^1 |h(x_1(\varsigma), I^{2\alpha-\delta} y(\varsigma) + \frac{x(0)}{\Gamma(\alpha-\delta+1)})| d\varsigma \\
&\quad + \frac{1}{m} \int_0^1 |h(x_2(\varsigma), I^{2\alpha-\delta} y(\varsigma) + \frac{x(0)}{\Gamma(\alpha-\delta+1)})| d\varsigma \\
&\leq \frac{1}{m} [(\sum_{k=1}^m a_k \|x_1\| - \sum_{k=1}^m a_k \|x_2\|)] - \frac{1}{m} \int_0^1 b_3 (|(x_1(\varsigma)| + |I^{2\alpha-\delta} y(\varsigma) + \frac{x(0)}{\Gamma(\alpha-\delta+1)}|) d\varsigma \\
&\quad + \frac{1}{m} \int_0^1 (|(x_2(\varsigma)| + |I^{2\alpha-\delta} y(\varsigma) + \frac{x(0)}{\Gamma(\alpha-\delta+1)}|) d\varsigma \\
&\leq \frac{1}{m} \|x_1 - x_2\| \sum_{k=1}^m a_k + \frac{b_3}{m} \|x_1 - x_2\|
\end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$\|x_1 - x_2\| (1 - (\frac{1}{m} \sum_{k=1}^m a_k + \frac{b_3}{m})) \leq 0 \quad \longrightarrow \quad x_1 = x_2$$

5. Continuous Dependency

Definition 1 (2.2) has a unique solution $x \in C(I)$ that depends continuously on x , if $\forall \epsilon > 0, \exists \delta > 0$, where

$$|x - x^*| \leq \delta \Rightarrow \|x - x^*\| \leq \epsilon$$

As long as x^* satisfies

$$x^*(t) = I^\alpha(y(t) + \frac{1}{m} [(\sum_{k=1}^m a_k x^*(\tau_k)) - \int_0^1 h(x^*(\varsigma), I^{2\alpha-\delta} y(\varsigma) + \frac{x^*(0)}{\Gamma(\alpha-\delta+1)})] d\varsigma)$$

Theorem 5.5 According to assumption (H_4) , (2.2) has a unique solution that depends continuously on x_0 .

Proof. suppose that the two functions $x(t)$ and $x^*(t)$ satisfy (2.2); then,

$$\begin{aligned}
|x(t) - x^*(t)| &= |I^\alpha(y(t) + \frac{1}{m}[(\sum_{k=1}^m a_k x(\tau_k)) - \int_0^1 h(x(\varsigma), I^{2\alpha-\delta}y(\varsigma)) \\
&\quad + \frac{x(0)}{\Gamma(\alpha - \delta + 1)}]d\varsigma] \\
&\quad - I^\alpha(y(t) - \frac{1}{m}[(\sum_{k=1}^m a_k x^*(\tau_k)) - \int_0^1 h(x^*(\varsigma), I^{2\alpha-\delta}y(\varsigma)) \\
&\quad + \frac{x^*(0)}{\Gamma(\alpha - \delta + 1)}]d\varsigma] \\
&\leq \frac{1}{m}[\sum_{k=1}^m a_k \|x\| - \sum_{k=1}^m a_k \|x^*\|] - \frac{1}{m} \int_0^1 b_3 (|(x(\varsigma)| + |I^{2\alpha-\delta}y(\varsigma) + \frac{x(0)}{\Gamma(\alpha - \delta + 1)}|)d\varsigma \\
&\quad + \frac{1}{m} \int_0^1 b_3 (|(x^*(\varsigma)| + |I^{2\alpha-\delta}y(\varsigma) + \frac{x^*(0)}{\Gamma(\alpha - \delta + 1)}|)d\varsigma \\
&\leq \frac{1}{m}[\|x - x^*\| \sum_{k=1}^m a_k] + \frac{b_3}{m} + [\|x - x^*\| + \frac{|x(0) - x^*(0)|}{\Gamma(\alpha - \delta + 1)}] \\
&\leq \frac{1}{m}[\|x - x^*\| \sum_{k=1}^m a_k] + \frac{b_3}{m} + [\|x - x^*\| + \frac{\delta}{\Gamma(\alpha - \delta + 1)}] \\
|x(t) - x^*(t)| &\leq \|x - x^*\|[\frac{1}{m} \sum_{k=1}^m a_k + \frac{b_3}{m}] + \frac{b_3 \delta}{m\Gamma(\alpha - \delta + 1)}
\end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$\|x - x^*\|(1 - (\frac{1}{m} \sum_{k=1}^m a_k + \frac{b_3}{m})) \leq \delta$$

and

$$\|x - x^*\| \leq \frac{\delta}{1 - (\frac{1}{m} \sum_{k=1}^m a_k + \frac{b_3}{m})} = \epsilon$$

Definition 2 (2.2) has a unique solution $x \in C(I)$ that depends continuously on y , if $\forall \epsilon > 0, \exists \delta > 0$, where

$$|y - y^*| \leq \delta \Rightarrow \|x - x^*\| \leq \epsilon$$

The integral equation for x^* is satisfied.

$$x^*(t) = I^\alpha(y(t) + \frac{1}{m}[(\sum_{k=1}^m a_k x^*(\tau_k)) - \int_0^1 h(x^*(\varsigma), I^{2\alpha-\delta}y(\varsigma) + \frac{x^*(0)}{\Gamma(\alpha - \delta + 1)}]d\varsigma]$$

Theorem 5.6 According to assumption (H_4) , (2.2) has a unique solution that depends continuously on y .

Proof. suppose that the two functions $x(t)$ and $x^*(t)$ satisfy (2.2); then,

$$\begin{aligned}
|x(t) - x^*(t)| &= |I^\alpha y(t) + \frac{1}{m} [(\sum_{k=1}^m a_k x(\tau_k)) - \int_0^1 h(x(\varsigma), I^{2\alpha-\delta} y(\varsigma) + \frac{x(0)}{\Gamma(\alpha-\delta+1)}) d\varsigma] \\
&\quad - I^\alpha y(t) - \frac{1}{m} [(\sum_{k=1}^m a_k x^*(\tau_k)) - \int_0^1 h(x^*(\varsigma), I^{2\alpha-\delta} y(\varsigma) + \frac{x^*(0)}{\Gamma(\alpha-\delta+1)}) d\varsigma]| \\
&= |\frac{1}{m} [(\sum_{k=1}^m a_k x(\tau_k)) - \int_0^1 h(x(\varsigma), I^{2\alpha-\delta} y(\varsigma) + \frac{x(0)}{\Gamma(\alpha-\delta+1)}) d\varsigma] \\
&\quad - \frac{1}{m} [(\sum_{k=1}^m a_k x^*(\tau_k)) - \int_0^1 h(x^*(\varsigma), I^{2\alpha-\delta} y(\varsigma) + \frac{x^*(0)}{\Gamma(\alpha-\delta+1)}) d\varsigma]| \\
&= |\frac{1}{m} \sum_{k=1}^m a_k I^\alpha (y(\tau_k) - y^*(\tau_k)) - \frac{1}{m} \int_0^1 h(x(\varsigma), I^{2\alpha-\delta} y(\varsigma) + \frac{x(0)}{\Gamma(\alpha-\delta+1)}) d\varsigma \\
&\quad + \frac{1}{m} \int_0^1 h(x^*(\varsigma), I^{2\alpha-\delta} y(\varsigma) + \frac{x^*(0)}{\Gamma(\alpha-\delta+1)}) d\varsigma| \\
&\leq \frac{\delta}{m\Gamma(\alpha+1)} \sum_{k=1}^m a_k + \frac{b_3}{m} [\|x - x^*\| + \frac{\|x - x^*\|}{\Gamma(\alpha-\delta+1)}]
\end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$\|x - x^*\| (1 - (\frac{b_3}{m} + \frac{b_3}{m\Gamma(\alpha-\delta+1)})) \leq \frac{\delta}{m\Gamma(\alpha+1)} \sum_{k=1}^m a_k$$

and

$$\|x - x^*\| \leq \frac{\frac{\delta}{m\Gamma(\alpha+1)} \sum_{k=1}^m a_k}{1 - (\frac{b_3}{m} + \frac{b_3}{m\Gamma(\alpha-\delta+1)})} = \epsilon$$

Definition 5.1 (2.2) has a unique solution $x \in C(I)$ that depends continuously on h , if $\forall \epsilon > 0, \exists \delta > 0$, where

$$|h(x(\varsigma), I^{2\alpha-\delta} y(\varsigma) + \frac{x(0)}{\Gamma(\alpha-\delta+1)}) - h^*(x(\varsigma), I^{2\alpha-\delta} y(\varsigma) + \frac{x(0)}{\Gamma(\alpha-\delta+1)})| \leq \delta \rightarrow \|x - x^*\| \leq \epsilon$$

where x^* satisfies

$$x^*(t) = I^\alpha y(t) + \frac{1}{m} [(\sum_{k=1}^m a_k x^*(\tau_k)) - \int_0^1 h^*(x^*(\varsigma), I^{2\alpha-\delta} y(\varsigma) + \frac{x(0)}{\Gamma(\alpha-\delta+1)}) d\varsigma]$$

Theorem 5.7 According to assumption (H_4) , (2.2) has a unique solution that depends continuously on h .

Proof. suppose that the two functions $x(t)$ and $x^*(t)$ satisfy (2.2); then,

$$\begin{aligned}
|x(t) - x^*(t)| &= |I^\alpha(y(t) + \frac{1}{m}[(\sum_{k=1}^m a_k x(\tau_k)) - \int_0^1 h(x(\varsigma), I^{2\alpha-\delta}y(\varsigma) + \frac{x(0)}{\Gamma(\alpha-\delta+1)})d\varsigma] \\
&\quad - I^\alpha(y(t) - \frac{1}{m}[(\sum_{k=1}^m a_k x^*(\tau_k)) - \int_0^1 h^*(x^*(\varsigma), I^{2\alpha-\delta}y(\varsigma) + \frac{x(0)}{\Gamma(\alpha-\delta+1)})d\varsigma])| \\
&= |\frac{1}{m}(\sum_{k=1}^m a_k x(\tau_k)) + \frac{1}{m} \int_0^1 h(x(\varsigma), I^{2\alpha-\delta}y(\varsigma) + \frac{x(0)}{\Gamma(\alpha-\delta+1)})d\varsigma \\
&\quad - \frac{1}{m}(\sum_{k=1}^m a_k x^*(\tau_k)) - \frac{1}{m} \int_0^1 h^*(x^*(\varsigma), I^{2\alpha-\delta}y(\varsigma) + \frac{x(0)}{\Gamma(\alpha-\delta+1)})d\varsigma \\
&\quad + \frac{1}{m} \int_0^1 h^*(x(\varsigma), I^{2\alpha-\delta}y(\varsigma) + \frac{x(0)}{\Gamma(\alpha-\delta+1)})d\varsigma \\
&\quad - \frac{1}{m} \int_0^1 h^*(x(\varsigma), I^{2\alpha-\delta}y(\varsigma) + \frac{x(0)}{\Gamma(\alpha-\delta+1)})d\varsigma| \\
&\leq \frac{\sum_{k=1}^m a_k}{m} \|x - x^*\| + \frac{1}{m} [\int_0^1 |h(x(\varsigma), I^{2\alpha-\delta}y(\varsigma) + \frac{x(0)}{\Gamma(\alpha-\delta+1)}) \\
&\quad - \int_0^1 h^*(x(\varsigma), I^{2\alpha-\delta}y(\varsigma) + \frac{x(0)}{\Gamma(\alpha-\delta+1)})d\varsigma| \\
&\quad + \frac{1}{m} [\int_0^1 |h^*(x(\varsigma), I^{2\alpha-\delta}y(\varsigma) + \frac{x(0)}{\Gamma(\alpha-\delta+1)})d\varsigma \\
&\quad - \int_0^1 h^*(x(\varsigma), I^{2\alpha-\delta}y(\varsigma) + \frac{x(0)}{\Gamma(\alpha-\delta+1)})d\varsigma| \\
&\leq \frac{\sum_{k=1}^m a_k}{m} \|x - x^*\| + \frac{\delta}{m} + \frac{b_3}{m} \|x - x^*\|
\end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$\|x - x^*\| (1 - (\frac{b_3}{m} + \frac{\sum_{k=1}^m a_k}{m})) \leq \frac{\delta}{m}$$

Thus,

$$\|x - x^*\| \leq \frac{\frac{\delta}{m}}{(1 - (\frac{b_3}{m} + \frac{\sum_{k=1}^m a_k}{m}))} = \epsilon$$

Now, we will use the following example to explain our results.

Example. Here we present a nonlinear integro-differential equation

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = t^4 e^{-t} + \frac{1}{2}(D^{\frac{3}{4}}x(t) + D^{\frac{1}{2}}(\frac{\sqrt{t}}{3} + \frac{1}{4}I^{\frac{2}{3}}x(t))) \quad (5.1)$$

with the nonlocal fractional-order integral condition

$$mx(0) + \int_0^1 ((\frac{\varsigma}{4})^2 + \frac{1}{2}I^{\frac{1}{2}}x(\varsigma))d\varsigma = \sum_{k=1}^m (\frac{1}{k(k+1)})x(\tau_k) \quad (5.2)$$

Thus

$$f_1(t, D^\alpha x(t), D^\beta f_2(t, I^\gamma x(t))) = t^4 e^{-t} + \frac{1}{2}(D^{\frac{3}{4}}x(t) + D^{\frac{1}{2}}(\frac{\sqrt{t}}{3} + \frac{1}{4}I^{\frac{2}{3}}x(t)))$$

$$f_2(t, I^\gamma x(t)) = \frac{\sqrt{t}}{3} + \frac{1}{4}I^{\frac{2}{3}}x(t), \quad t \in I$$

When $t = 1$, theorem (2.1) holds

$$m_1(t) = t^4 e^{-t} \in L^1[0, 1], \quad m_2(t) = \frac{\sqrt{t}}{3} \in L^1[0, 1]$$

$$k_1 = \frac{1}{2}, \quad k_2 = \frac{1}{4}, \quad \alpha = \frac{3}{4}, \quad \beta = \frac{1}{2}, \quad \gamma = \frac{2}{3}, \quad \delta = \frac{1}{4}$$

$$m_2^* = \sup D^\beta |m_2(t)|$$

$$= \sup I^{1-\beta} \frac{d}{dt}(\frac{\sqrt{t}}{3}) = 0.295409$$

and in the same manner, we can obtain m_1^*

$$m_1^* = \sup I^{1-\alpha} |m_1(t)| = 0.264015$$

As a result of (3), we have

$$r_1 - \frac{1}{2} \frac{(r_1 + 0.295409)}{\Gamma(1.25)} = 0.264015$$

Then, $r_1 = 0.952279$ is a positive number. Hence, at least one solution exists for problems (5.1) and (5.2).

6. Conclusion

Throughout this paper, we have discussed the solvability of the nonlocal problem (1.1)-(1.2) and proved that solution $x \in C(I)$ exists. As part of our work, we have demonstrated a few existing results for a boundary value problem involving fractional order differential inclusion with nonlocal integral boundary. Next, we have demonstrated the existence of maximal and minimal solutions to problem(1.1)-(1.2). As a result, sufficient conditions have been established for the uniqueness of solutions and continuous dependence of the solution. Finally, an example is provided to illustrate our results.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- [1] Aicha, S.; Merad, A. Solvability of nonlinear fractional integro-differential equation with nonlocal condition. *Arab. J. Math. Sci.* 2023, 29, 172–190. [Google Scholar] [CrossRef]
- [2] J. P. Aubin, A. Cellina, *Differential inclusions: Set-valued maps and viability theory*, Berlin: Springer, 2012.
- [3] Z. B. Bai, Solvability for a class of fractional m-point boundary value problem at resonance, *Comput. Math. Appl.*, 62 (2011), 1292–1302. doi: 10.1016/j.camwa.2011.03.003. doi: 10.1016/j.camwa.2011.03.003
- [4] J. Banaś, J.; Lecko, M.; El-Sayed, W.G. Existence theorems for some quadratic integral equations. *J. Math. Anal. Appl.* 1998, 222, 276–285. [Google Scholar] [CrossRef] [Green Version]
- [5] Banaś, J.; Zajac, T. A new approach to the theory of functional integral equations of fractional order. *J. Math. Anal. Appl.* 2011, 375, 375–387. [Google Scholar] [CrossRef] [Green Version]
- [6] Banaś, J.; Caballero, J.; Rocha, J.; Sadarangani, K. Monotonic solutions of a class of quadratic integral equations of Volterra type. *Comput. Math. Appl.* 2005, 49, 943–952. [Google Scholar] [CrossRef] [Green Version]
- [7] Bader, R.; Papageorgiou, N.S. Nonlinear multivalued boundary value problems, *Discussiones Mathematicae Differential Inclusions. Control Optim.* 2001, 21, 127–148. [Google Scholar]
- [8] Boucherif, A.; Precup, R. On the nonlocal initial value problem for first order differential equations. *Fixed Point Theory* 2003, 4, 205–212. [Google Scholar]
- [9] El Borai, M.; Abbas, M.I. On Some Integro-Differential Equations of Fractional Orders Involving Caratheodory Nonlinearities. *Int. J. Mod. Math.* 2007, 2, 41–52. [Google Scholar]
- [10] Curtain, R.F.; Pritchard, A.J. *Functional Analysis in Modern Applied Mathematics*; Academic Press: Cambridge, MA, USA, 1977. [Google Scholar]
- [11] Alama, H. M. . (2024). On some spectral properties for nonlocal boundary value problems of nonlinear differential inclusion.
- [12] A. M. A. El-Sayed, A. G. Ibrahim, Set-valued integral equation of fractional-orders, *Appl. Math. Comput.*, 118 (2001), 113–121. doi: 10.1016/S0096-3003(99)00087-9. doi: 10.1016/S0096-3003(99)00087-9

- [13] A. M. A. El-Sayed, E.M.A Hamdallah, and H.M.A Alama. "Multiple solutions of a Sturm-Liouville boundary value problem of nonlinear differential inclusion with nonlocal integral conditions." *AIMS Mathematics* 7.6 (2022): 11150-11164.
- [14] Kilbas, A.A.; Srivastava, H.M.; Trujillo, J.J. *Theory and Applications of Fractional Differential Equations*; Elsevier: Amsterdam, The Netherlands, 2006.
- [15] N. Kosmatov, A boundary value problem of fractional order at resonance, *Electron. J. Differ. Eq.*, 2010 (2010), 1–10.
- [16] Podlubny, I.; *Fractional Differential Equations*, Acad. press, San Diego-New York-London 1999.
- [17] Sumelka, W. Fractional viscoplasticity. *Mech. Res. Commun.* 2014, 56, 31–36. [Google Scholar] [CrossRef]
- [18] Subashini, R.; Jothimani, K.; Nisar, K.S.; Ravichandran, C. New results on non-local functional integrodifferential equations via Hilfer fractional derivative. *Alex. Eng. J.* 2020, 59, 2891–2899. [Google Scholar] [CrossRef]
- [19] Zeng, S.; Rădulescu, V.D.; Winkert, P. Double phase implicit Obstacle problems with convection and multivalued mixed boundary value conditions. *SIAM J. Math. Anal.* 2022, 54, 1–25. [Google Scholar] [CrossRef]